

EFFICIENT MOBILE VIDEO-ON-DEMAND WITH HAND-OFF SUPPORT

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ABSTRACT

Because of the varied capabilities of servers and clients in terms of resources and processing complexity, no Video-on-Demand (VoD) technique can provide efficient and absolute solutions in all circumstances. The popular factor of videos is a challenging issue to be kept in mind in order to minimize the resource utilization of VoD system, thereby enhancing the quality of the service and gaining user satisfaction. To use the popularity details of the videos of a VoD service and allocate necessary amount of resources, there are many schemes that have been proposed but most of them are short of successfully managing all the elements of the service. Hence, we have proposed a new scheme that is expected to bring noticeable improvement in the service. To be more specific, the scheme minimizes the user's waiting time and also successfully handles the hand-off procedure for a moving client during downloading a video segment providing efficient service to clients.

Keywords: Video-on-Demand, mobi-VoD, MANET, Hand-Off, waiting time and re-download time, and re-download

INTRODUCTION

With the initiation of the Internet, efficient and timely distribution of electronic contents among clients around the world has become a demanding issue. Key ingredients of these contents are small web objects containing texts and images that require very little transmission time. Consequently, a web server is expected to serve a large number of requests for these objects from many clients with tolerable delays. In reality, however, server's link to the Internet acts as a bottleneck, which can severely increase the delay beyond clients' expectation even for such smaller objects when the server is hit by a sudden surge of requests. While intelligent web caching and geographically distributed server mirroring can ease these problems significantly, the Internet still remains vulnerable to the distribution of

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large contents such as video clips, especially when the demand increases due to popularity. As the transmission time of these contents is significantly high, caching and/ or mirroring can play little role in reducing the waiting time of clients who are being served from the same server with link capacity less than the collective bandwidth requirement of the requests. This is due to the Internet protocol's prevailing unicast transmission where a dedicated connection between the server and the client is created for each request to deliver web contents even if many other clients are requesting the same contents at the same time.

Latest Internet protocols have addressed this problem by introducing multicast and broadcast transmission to share an Internet connection as much as possible while distributing contents to a group of clients and thus, open up a new horizon in the field of popular large content distribution, widely known as video-on-demand (VoD).

Figure 1: VoD architecture

The server retrieves video data from the video archive and delivers video streams through the Internet to the end clients. In general, VoD aims for delivering any video to any viewer either instantly or within a short delay after the request has been placed by the viewer¹. The

techniques evolved in VoD are not necessarily applicable to only video distribution where the popularity trend is typically highly skewed toward the very few top ranked videos. Any large content distribution problem exhibiting some popularity trend can benefit from these techniques as well.

Some of the applications of VoD include movie-on-demand, distance learning, interactive video games, news-on-demand, tele-shopping, and online advertisement. A typical VoD system is implemented as client-server architecture (shown in Figure 1). A VoD server consists of a high-end computer (or a cluster of such computers), which stores a large number of videos into the storage. The term “channel”, acting as an abstraction to mask the physical details of the underlying network, is defined as an allocation of a certain amount of communication resources on a certain communication path. The delivery network may be the Internet, a fiber cable network, or a satellite broadcast network.

However, the modern VoD systems are far more complex. Simply broadcasting a very hot video at regular intervals over a number of channels is not an attractive solution, since waiting time decreases only linearly with the number of channels. Segmented broadcasting, where a video is partitioned into a number of segments and then several segments are broadcast periodically over a channel using time-domain multiplexing, can potentially reduce the waiting time exponentially, if either segment size increases or corresponding channel capacity decreases gradually. Another way of reducing the waiting time is to develop hybrid systems that allow a client, who has just missed a broadcast or multicast transmission, to join that transmission immediately by patching the missing initial portion through a unicast stream.

In this VoD system our main focus will be on:

- Modelling a Video-on-Demand technique to handle the hand-off procedure during downloading a video for a moving client;
- Modelling a Video-on-Demand technique to reduce the client waiting time in both download a segment in a new cluster and the re-download; and
- Modelling a Video-on-Demand technique to establish a seamless channel transition.

PREVIOUS WORKS

VoD system is an interactive multimedia system working like cable television; the difference is that the client can select a movie from a large video database stored at a distant video server. Individual clients in an area are able to watch different programs when they wish to, making the system a realization of the video rental shop brought into home. It is interesting and worthwhile to design a VoD system for Mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) (Qasim, 2010). We need to first know about the architecture and characteristics of the MANET.

MANET

Mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) as shown in Figure 2 represent complex distributed systems that comprise wireless mobile nodes that can freely and dynamically self-organize into arbitrary and temporary, “Ad-hoc” network topologies, allowing people and devices to seamlessly interconnect in areas with no pre-existing communication infrastructure, e.g., disaster recovery environments. The proliferation of mobile computing and communication devices (e.g., cell phones, laptops, handheld digital devices, personal digital assistants, or wearable computers) is driving a revolutionary change in our information society. A major goal toward the 4G Wireless evolutions is the providing of pervasive computing environments that can seamlessly and ubiquitously support users in accomplishing their tasks, in accessing information or communicating with other users at anytime, anywhere, and from any device. With the availability of ultra-high bandwidth of up to 100 Mbps, multimedia services can be supported efficiently; ubiquitous computing is enabled with enhanced system mobility and portability support, and location- based services are all expected.

Figure 2: Example of MANET

AD-HOC NETWORKING ISSUES

In general, mobile Ad-hoc networks are formed dynamically by an autonomous system of mobile nodes that are connected via wireless links without using the existing network

infrastructure or centralized administration (Chlamtac, Conti, Jennifer, & Liu 2003). For communicating with nodes that reside beyond this range, the node needs to use intermediate nodes to relay the messages hop by hop.

- The wireless medium has neither absolute, nor readily observable boundaries outside of which stations are known to be unable to receive network frames;
- The channel is unprotected from outside signals;
- The wireless medium is significantly less reliable than wired media;
- The channel has time-varying and asymmetric propagation properties; and
- Hidden-terminal and exposed-terminal phenomena may occur.

Figure 3: A simple MANET Architecture

There is no default router available in ad hoc system, every node acts as a router and forwards each other's packets to enable information sharing between mobile hosts. In mobile ad hoc networks, because nodes can move arbitrarily, the network topology, which is typically multi-hop, can change frequently and unpredictably, resulting in route changes, frequent network partitions, and possibly packet losses. Many mobile ad hoc network applications involve large networks with tens of thousands of nodes, as found for example, in sensor networks and tactical networks. Scalability is critical to the successful deployment of these networks. Figure 3 above shows a simple architecture of MANET.

VoD

The simplest VoD (Tran, 2004) is implemented through dedicated unicast channels that give the clients exclusive control over the channel with instantaneous access.

There exist mainly 2 types of VoD architecture: True VoD and Near VoD

TRUE VoD

The simplest VoD is implemented through dedicated unicast channels that give the clients exclusive control over the channel with instantaneous access and thus, referred to as true VoD (TVoD). TVoD systems are not scalable. Since the load on the server increases linearly with the viewer arrival rate, TVoD can cause severe bottleneck at the server-side at high viewer arrival rates. Obviously, TVoD systems are not scalable and thus, not suitable for a large population of viewers where each viewer requests asynchronously for a video of choice.

NEAR VoD

It can reduce the server bandwidth requirement by forcing two or more viewers requesting the same video to share a single stream by batching requests over a specified interval and thus, introducing a short client waiting time.

As the internet user is increasing rapidly in this recent years and people always want to entertain by videos but there is not enough time for users to see videos telecasting in TV. For this reason they are now depending mainly on VoD service as this service delivers the requested video to the client and client can easily enjoy that video with his demand. But some users may be moving during downloading a video segment from server. Our main focus is how a client can request to the Local Forwarder and how the Local Forwarder get that requested video segment from the main Central Multimedia Server and how they deliver that video segment to the client. There may be some problem for moving client during downloading a video segment and the client may be re-download the whole video segment again and again if it moves so fast and cross a particular LF's cluster before downloading a full video segment. We worked mainly with this hand-off topic and how to efficiently hand-off a client with mobility support. And also we proposed a solution where the client will not have to face any waiting delay during downloading a video segment.

PROPOSED SYSTEM/ SCHEME

There have been a number of schemes that have been developed to attack the major issues of the VoD system with Ad-Hoc Architecture, namely, MobiVoD (A Video-on-Demand system designed for mobile ad hoc networks).

We propose in this section MobiVoD, The solution for providing VoD services to mobile users containing ad hoc connections. Although many existing Internet VoD techniques (Gurber, Hua & Park, 2000) are based on the client/ server approach, we argue that this approach does not work well for MANETs simply because wireless bandwidth cannot support many clients using separate connection channels. MobiVoD employs broadcasting at the video server to disseminate videos to wireless clients; specifically, we propose to use Periodic Broadcasting (Hua, 1997 & Hu, 2001). Using this approach, a video is divided into several segments, each repeatedly broadcast on a separate communication channel. A client receives a video by tuning to one or more channels at a time to download the data. A clear advantage of Periodic Broadcasting is that the system can accommodate any number of clients.

A client in any service area can receive the broadcast packets. The playback procedure at a client follows the simple algorithm below:

PROCEDURE CLIENT PLAYBACK

- Step1: Detect a local forwarder LF
- Step 2: Find the channel from LF that is going to broadcast the first segment soonest
- Step 3: Wait to join that broadcast
- Step 4: Download and play the video data from this channel
- Step 5: Quit this channel

PROPOSED SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

In the mobi-VoD architecture in ad hoc networking we know that clients may be mobile and they may also be static sometime. At that time when the client wants any video s/he requests for that video to the local forwarder. The local forwarder then requests the main server for that video. The main server then delivers the first segment of that video to the local forwarder; in turn the local forwarder provides that video segment to the client. The client then downloads that video segment. And as soon as it starts downloading the first segment, it sends a second request message for the second segment of that particular video.

In the mobile Video-on-Demand, we know there are three main components: (a) the Video server (Video Archive), (b) the Local Forwarder and (c) the Client. Here the task for each component is different. Our main target is to hand-off client efficiently during downloading and to optimize the waiting time to start a new segment download and to optimize the delay

time to re-download the video segment again. Figure 4 below aptly explains this phenomenon. The three components are wirelessly connected as the system architecture in Figure 4 shows. Here the central media server or the main video server is connected with the local forwarders wirelessly and the local forwarders are also connected between them. The clients are also connected with the local forwarders wirelessly. Here the local forwarders can use multichannel as it can work like a main video server.

But the client can use only one channel as the client is a mobile client. So the client can't download and send message at the same time. The task for client depends on its free channel. If the client is downloading a video segment, its channel is using and at that time it can't send any message to the local forwarders. So the client must need to use its channel to send a message to the local forwarders just before starting downloading a new video segment.

Figure 4: System Architecture for Proposed Mobi-VoD

SYSTEM OVERVIEW

This section will illustrate how the system works in our proposed architecture. This section also discusses how the client sends a message to a local forwarder; how the local forwarder sends that message to its neighboring Local Forwarder's; and how the information about the clients are stored into the Database which LF's use and also how the entire system works.

CLIENTS MESSAGE INITIALIZATION

Figure 5 shows how the message sent to the local forwarder from the client like a packet and the packet will contain the Client ID (CID), Video ID (VID) and the Video Segment ID and the time of the segment downloaded (for starting a new segment request this time will be 0.00 min), but if the client was downloading a video segment then it will send the time up to which it downloaded.

Figure 5: Client message format to Local Forwarder

Whenever a client sends a request message to LF, LF forwards the message to the LF's who are at one hop distance of the present LF. At the same time, the Local forwarder creates a channel for the client and sends the requested segment using that channel in a reactive fashion. The reactive fashion mainly works to deliver video segment on request. So when the client requests for a video, the Local Forwarder delivers that video segment to the client by using reactive fashion and broadcast that video segment by using only one channel. When the download of the present segment is finished, the client instantly sends a new download request to the Local Forwarder and start playing the video segment. When the client is playing the video segment in the meantime the download of the next video segment will be completed and it will automatically adjust after the first segment. So the client doesn't need to wait for a long time to download. The client only needs to wait for downloading the first video segment. After downloading the first video segment, the client doesn't need to wait anymore.

DATABASE OF LOCAL FORWARDER (LF)

For storing the information of the clients under the cluster of the LF's, all the LF uses a database. The Database keeps the information about two types of client:

1. Present Client: If a client is currently present under the cluster of a Local Forwarder, that specific client will be stored as a Present client of that specific Local Forwarder.
2. Upcoming Client: If any Client is not present in Local Forwarder's cluster but in the cluster at one hop distance, the information of that client will be stored as an upcoming client.

The Database will store the information given below:

- Contains user info.
- Contains video segments for clients.
- Present LF should contain 1 segment for 1 specific client.
- One hop distance LF's have to contain at least 2 video segments for specific client.
- If a new message for an existing client comes, previous info will overwrite.

TIME DELAY OPTIMIZATION FOR RE-DOWNLOAD

When a client is downloading a video segment, it can also move at the same time and during downloading a video segment it enters into a new cluster of a new Local Forwarder, at that time if the new LF doesn't know which video segment it was downloading then the LF can't deliver the specific video segment to that client immediately. The Client must need to send a new download request to the new LF and the new LF need to download that specific video segment from the Central Multimedia Server and then it can deliver the video segment to that client which is so much time consuming. If the LF knows which video segment the client is currently downloading and if it stores that video segment then when the client enters into its cluster and send a request for that video segment it can easily deliver the video segment. The client doesn't need to re-download the video segment from the beginning. The downloading process from the part of a video segment is possible. But the point is why the new LF or the neighbor LF always needs to download the next video segment of that video which the client is currently downloading? The reason is only for safety. Just think, if the client completes its download of a segment just before entering into the new LF's cluster, then if the new LF doesn't have the next segment it needs to download the next segment from the Central Media Server and then the LF can deliver it to the client. So it will take a long time and the client has to face a long time delay. So, if the new LF or the neighbor LF previously knows which segment the client is downloading and stores that segment including the next segment then it will be easier for the new LF to deliver the video segment to the client without any time delay. During downloading a video segment if the client enters into a new cluster, it will send a message to that LF. The message contains the time of that video up to which the video was downloaded.

Figure 6: Client Message to new LF under which cluster it just entered

When the new LF gets this message it immediately divides that specific video segment into two parts:

Part 1: the part size will be equal to the size downloaded depending on time.

Part 2: remaining part required to download.

This segmentation is possible as the LF works like a video server and as the video server can divide any video into a number of segments and broadcast them. The LF also can divide the video segments into parts. But here there will be only two parts and the partition size will not be equal like staggered broadcasting. Here the sizes are different.

As the Central Multimedia Server uses staggered broadcasting, the video segments and uses channels to broadcast those segments, clients can easily find the required video segment and the channel which is now starting to broadcast the requested segment and can download the video segment from that channel. Other channels were unused. But here, when the LF partitioned a specific video segment into 2 parts, which the client was downloading before entering into its cluster and the download was not properly completed, the client will use reactive broadcasting scheme for broadcasting the remaining part needed to be download. So here only one channel will be used by the LF to broadcast the remaining part of that specific video segment.

Figure 7: The Partition of the Video Segment

As here the client can download the remaining part of that specific video segment which it was downloading, the problem of re-downloading a video segment from the beginning is optimized near to zero. So, here our final target is also being completed. The time delay for client to re-download any video segment is optimized.

TASKS FOR LF

The tasks for LF can be simply explained by looking at the flow chart shown below-

Figure 8: Flow-Chart for tasks of LF

ADVANTAGES OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

- New request waiting time optimized
- Re-download waiting time optimized
- Partition of a specific segment is possible
- Download from a specific portion
- Advantage of knowing client information early
- Waste of channel optimized
- The hand-off problem resolved

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In our thesis, we have optimized several clients' waiting time, wastage of channel and also we successfully handled the hand-off technique for a moving client during downloading a video segment. The proofs and achievements are explained below:

EFFICIENTLY HAND-OFF

When a client is moving during downloading a video segment, the entire neighbor already knows the segment which the client is downloading. When a client enters in the cluster of a new Local Forwarder, it will not face any problem for downloading the video segment it was downloading under the earlier cluster. It means that the hand-off technique is successfully made efficient.

WAITING DELAY OPTIMIZATION FOR NEW DOWNLOAD REQUEST AND RE-DOWNLOAD

When a client enters into the cluster of the neighbor Local Forwarder and sends a request for downloading the video segment he was downloading, the Local Forwarder can easily deliver that video segment to the client by making a partition of that video segment based on the time of that video segment up to which the client has already downloaded. Thus, the client can easily download the remaining part of that video segment. Here the waiting time for both re-downloading and sending a new request to the LF and in turn, the LF's downloading from main server and delivering the segment to the client is optimized. In this way, the system is likely to be more efficient and successful in the optimization of time delay for the client.

CHANNEL WASTAGE OPTIMIZATION

As the Local Forwarder makes a partition of the video segment which the client was downloading before entering into its cluster and then delivers only the remaining part of the video segment to download by using only a single channel by reactive fashion, so here we can easily say that, the wastage of the channel is optimized.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Recently, VoD has greatly improved to serve people's need. With the availability of the fast internet, the implementation of several VoD networks is very much plausible now. The main goal of the VoD is to serve as many users as possible with very little latency. Researchers are trying to introduce such schemes which can serve the purpose to a great extent. This research has attempted to contribute to the domain of improved and improvised VoD scheme.

The aim of this research was to propose a new VoD scheme that not only does the hand-off problem solution but also solve the problems of waiting time of clients. Our main goal was to successfully hand-off a client during downloading a video and moving from one LF's cluster

to another to optimize the time delay of re-downloading a video segment from the beginning; and also the time delay for sending a new request to a new LF for the video segment it was downloading. It seems that our proposed scheme can address these problems to a great extent.

There are, however, some limitations of the proposed scheme. They are: server overloading for many clients downloading at same time and longer waiting time due to larger number of clients. In the future, further research is required to mitigate the limitations of this proposed scheme.

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